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Labor in Flux

A Case Study on Flexibilization and Precarization of Work

in the Hungarian Electronics Industry

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Abstract

The phenomenon of flexibilization and precarization of work within the electronics industry has become a growing concern in the field of social sciences, including sociology. For employers in manufacturing, to reduce costs and enhance competitiveness it is crucial to adapt the various components of production – including the workforce – in a flexible manner to accommodate changes in production and market conditions. In Hungary, this is coupled with a regulatory environment and subsidies favorable to employers, often to the neglect of the interests of workers. As a case study, this thesis examines the working conditions in the Hungarian electronics sector and also explores the implementation of practices that lead to precarious and flexible working conditions, as well as the strategies that workers adopt in response. This is done by analyzing empirical data gathered during field research with the workers of an electronics industry factory in Hungary. The data includes qualitative interviews with workers, work-related documents, and relevant statistical information. The findings show that the factory under study practices various methods that lead to precarious and flexible working conditions. These practices include low basic wages, sometimes excessive overtime or compulsory leave according to production needs, typically with short notice for overtime, unstable forms of employment such as temporary agency work, and other precarious working conditions resulting in high levels of job insecurity. In response to these, workers primarily employ individual adaptive strategies, using existing channels in the workplace. Additionally, workers' limited room for maneuver is further reduced by the lack of institutionalized means of collective advocacy and the fragmentation of the workforce in terms of the form of employment and ethnicity. This paper focuses on temporary workers and migrant workers from Ukraine and the Philippines, who are particularly exposed to asymmetric labor relations.

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1. Introduction

Like any social phenomenon, the rise of precarious work and the surge of flexible working conditions are historically driven processes. Due to the global expansion and development of capitalism, there has been a concurrent rise in the flexibilization of both production processes and the workforce, increasing from the end of the 20th century. This has led to the restructuring of labor relations, a decrease in the bargaining power of labor, and the deindustrialization of some regions in parallel with the industrialization of others, with increased use of migrant labor (Harvey, 1989). During this development, in the context of the electronics industry and automotive sector, the term "foxconnization," coined by Boy Lüthje (2022), has been used to describe the intensified exploitation of workers in global electronics supply chains, represented by the labor practices of Foxconn Technology Group. Foxconn has faced criticism for its harsh working conditions, including low wages and excessive overtime, which have been linked to worker suicides and protests at Foxconn facilities worldwide (Chan et al., 2020). This process sets the stage for understanding the labor landscape in the Hungarian electronics sector. As a semi-peripheral country embedded within the capitalist world system. Hungary's reliance on working capital from core states, and its economic cooperation with other semi-peripheral regions, coupled with the relative proximity of the European markets makes it an optimal ground for outsourcing production. As a result, Hungary has adopted a strategy of undercutting local labor regulations and wages to attract foreign investments (Czifrusz et al., 2019; Éber, 2020; Éber et al., 2019; Gerócs & Pinkasz, 2019; Plank & Staritz, 2013). Consequently, this contributes to the rising precariousness of labor in Hungarian manufacturing. However, it is temporary agency workers and migrant workers that bear a disproportionate burden of these asymmetrical labor relations (Meszmann, 2016, 2018; Meszmann & Fedyuk, 2019).

As a case study, this thesis examines the working conditions of a factory in the Hungarian electronics sector. It explores the implementation of practices that lead to precarious and flexible working conditions, as well as the strategies that workers adopted in response to these conditions. It seeks to understand how global and regional developments and global social changes shape intra-factory relations and working conditions. It is important to understand the room for maneuvering available to workers in an asymmetric and coercive industrial work environment. As such, this thesis offers critical and up-to-date insights

into a classic sociological problem, to examine the social relations between labor and capital.

The research attempts to combine theories of global social change with regional industrial reports and structuralist approaches to the issue of agency. At the beginning of the paper, the relevant literature on the regulation of the labor force and its relation to the flexibilization and precarization of work is presented. Followed by the history and description of the general working conditions in the Hungarian electronics industry. Then the issue of consent and coercion are discussed, and the possibilities on what types of strategies can occur at individual, interpersonal, and collective levels, and what broader factors can influence them. The text continues with key contexts: the rise of temporary work agencies, and the presence of foreign workers in Hungary. After this, the study outlines the research questions, hypotheses, and methodology, including participant demographics and field research challenges. Finally, the relevant findings, discussion, and conclusions are presented.

A limitation of the study is that the research was not designed to examine the adaptive strategies of the workers. It was not part of the interview guide, resulting in a partial and less systematic explanation of this topic. Furthermore, the use of qualitative data and analysis limits the generalizability, as working conditions and flexibilization of labor may be different in similar plants in the region. Not to mention that, due to the difficulties of fieldwork and sampling, the empirical data, with few exceptions, is based almost entirely on the experiences of migrant and temporary workers. Only remotely approximating the conditions and adaptation strategies of local workers.

This drawback also provides the strength of the paper, illustrating the effects of temporary work agency employment, a form of employment that has become increasingly popular in the manufacturing sector. It also gives an insight into the situation of workers from war-stricken Ukraine and third-country national workers, with a focus on people from the Philippines. A topic that is still relatively under-researched and under-discussed in the Hungarian sociological community.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Regulation, flexibilization, and precarization of work

The regulation of the labor force in modern capitalism has a complex and evolving history. It emerged from the dissolution of traditional peasant societies, urbanization, and proletarianization, introducing wage-earning workers (Marx, 1949; Polányi, 2004). From the 19th century, technological advancements led to significant gains in labor productivity. These improvements were achieved through various measures, including the modernization and rationalization of production and control mechanisms, the simplification of tasks, the implementation of performance-based pay systems, and mass production peaking in Fordist production. These changes also gave rise to distinct power dynamics in workplaces, designed to maintain production continuity, control, discipline, and motivate workers, adapted to the specific demands of production (Foucault, 1995; Kuczi, 2011). In the next stage of industrial development, Post-Fordism offered new technologies, new organizational types, and new forms of production like: “just in time” production and the process called "vertical disintegration", which has led to the widespread adoption of practices such as sub-contracting and outsourcing production on an international level, fundamentally transforming the nature of work as well (Harvey, 1989). A crucial prerequisite for the effectiveness of capitalist production is the flexible adaptation of its diverse components – including the labor force – to the changing dynamics of production and market conditions. The flexibility of working conditions therefore plays a prominent role in enabling a more efficient utilization of the working time and the labor force for employers, reducing production costs, enhancing competitiveness, and ultimately increasing the profitability of capital (Timár, 1988).

It is important to note, however, that the regulation and the organization of work and production is not a linear process. These transformations are associated with the cyclical nature of the economy and capital accumulation, and institutional changes accommodated with it (Kotz et al., 1994; Lippit, 2010). Since the end of the 20th century, there has been a new era in globalization, with a significant shift in the form of capitalist accumulation and production. All of which is accompanied by a reduction in the turnover time of capital (Harvey, 1989). This increase in globalization also led to an increase in global labor migration. This process is also cyclical and is triggered by market forces that expand into peripheral and semi-peripheral regions, during the development of global capitalism

which erodes existing livelihood strategies and socio-economic institutions. As a result, migrants become geographically mobile and strive to adjust to spatially unevenly distributed opportunities. To this end, various political narratives, state regulations, formal and informal institutions emerged over time to regulate and facilitate these processes (Böröcz & Portes, 1989; Massey, 1990, 1999; Melegh, 2004, 2023; Melegh & Csányi, 2021).

While the flexibilization of working conditions offers employers advantages, it presents a diverse range of difficulties for workers in the form of the precarization of work. This refers to the erosion of standard employment arrangements, low wages, limited job security, and other unfavorable working conditions (Della Porta et al., 2015; Lewchuk, 2020; Melges et al., 2022). Additionally, migrant workers, who are frequently employed in low-skilled, temporary jobs, are particularly vulnerable to precarization (Meszmann, 2018).

2.2. The history of electronics manufacturing in Hungary

Hungary has a long history of electronics manufacturing, starting from the 19th century, producing products for electronic infrastructure. Companies like Ganz Works expanded into electrical equipment manufacturing when gained access to advanced technologies by the 20th century. The subsequent state-socialist era, marked by nationalization, witnessed an expansion of production, notably in the field of telecommunications engineering (Czirfusz, 2022, p. 6; Perényi et al., 2012, p. 15). After the 1990s a wave of privatization in parallel with an upswing in the global electronics industry provided new momentum for Hungary's electronics industry. From the early 2000s, several global companies had established a presence in the country. Popularity is attributed to tax benefits, low export tariffs, a cheap labor force, government subsidies, and a strategic location near the European markets. The global economic crisis of 2008 left its mark on the industry, causing closures and relocations, but the industry gradually recovered (Meszmann, 2016; Perényi et al., 2012; Sass, 2015). By 2020, the sector contributed nearly 7% to Hungary's Gross Value Added (GVA), positively impacting rural employment (Czirfusz, 2022, pp. 7–8).

2.3. Working conditions in the Hungarian electronics industry

Working conditions in the electronics industry are strongly influenced by the efforts of companies to standardize work processes, improve efficiency, and reduce costs. Vertical disintegration and outsourcing separate labor-intensive processes from knowledge-intensive and capital-intensive ones, creating distinct labor divisions and wage structures within the value chain (Plank & Staritz, 2013). The Hungarian government's strategic partnerships with key companies have demonstrated a commitment to industrial development but raised concerns about working conditions. Like other sectors, the industry under review has a high turnover rate, job insecurity remains an issue, and mobility channels for blue-collar workers are almost non-existent (Czirfusz, 2022; Perényi et al., 2012). Moreover, the industry is also characterized by precarious forms of employment such as fixed-term contracts and temporary agency work. Temporary work agencies (TWAs) are prevalent in the sector, as transnational corporations rely heavily on them. In many cases, the number of temporary workers may reach or even exceed the number of core workers, especially during periods of peak production and market fluctuations, deteriorating the working conditions for other workers as well (Meszmann, 2016; Perényi et al., 2012).

To get an overall picture of the electronics industry from the perspective of its workers, the following chapters will delve into the working conditions of the Hungarian electronics industry, by reviewing and synthesizing key studies from authors like Márton Czirfusz (2022) who provides the most up to date and comprehensive sectoral analysis on the Hungarian electronics industry, Zsófia Perényi (2012) and her colleagues, who made a comprehensive field study in four electronics manufacturing plant in Hungary, and other heavily related articles from authors like Tibor Meszmann (2016, 2018) and others. The aim of synthesizing these works is to demonstrate that the most common workplace issues have persisted for more than a decade.

2.3.1. Working hours

The Hungarian Labour Code (2011) allows employees to work for 40-48 hours per week, with a limit of 12 hours per day. Employers can require up to 250 hours per month, with a possible extra 150 hours by mutual agreement. Due to the non-stop nature of production, three-shift work schedules are common. Additionally, pay slips often misrepresent actual

hours worked, and employees willingly take on overtime (Czirfusz, 2022; Perényi et al., 2012).

The changing market environment affects working hours, promoting the adoption of time-banking systems. The time-banking system serves as a complex practice used by employers to mitigate the seasonality of production and demand by allocating and accounting for overtime and bonuses over several months (Czirfusz, 2022; Perényi et al., 2012; Plank & Staritz, 2013). Research by Perényi and her colleagues (2012) reveals that management advocates the time-banking system to prevent seasonal layoffs during periods of downtime. However, employees often perceive the system as unfair, and as a tactic that employers use to reduce their overtime payments. Furthermore, in the absence of a time-banking system, employers may still manipulate working hours to match production demands. The management can still order workers to work 72 hours (12 hours/6 days) while other days in the month may have reduced hours or even days off, effectively reducing overtime pay (Perényi et al., 2012).

Employers must give at least 7 days or up to 4 days' notice for overtime and extra shifts. However, employers regularly give short notice or send home temporary workers, leading to irregular scheduling, lack of transparency, and lower wages (Czirfusz, 2022; Plank & Staritz, 2013). This is evidenced by the relatively high number of incorrect working time records and faulty scheduling documents discovered during labor inspections in the sectors, as reported by Czirfusz (2022). Breaks are also insufficient for workers to cover everything that needs to be done during such intervals due to slow operation of entry gates and other security measures (Perényi et al., 2012).

2.3.2. Wages

The most significant problem with wages in the electronics industry is that workers rely heavily on bonuses and overtime to cover living costs. This is particularly true for workers with families, even in two-income households (Czirfusz, 2022; Fedyuk & Meszmann, 2018; Perényi et al., 2012). In the electronics industry, various bonuses and overtime allowances are added to the basic wage, and the employer is also required to cover the employee's travel expenses to some extent. Workers are also entitled to a wage supplement during overtime, for working on public holidays, and for working outside regular working hours (between 6 PM and 6 AM) (Czirfusz, 2022; Perényi et al., 2012).

Even though minimum wage regulations apply to agency/migrant workers in the same way as for core/domestic workers, there is a disparity in wages between unskilled and skilled workers (Czirfusz, 2022). As a result, operator wages tend to converge around or just above the living wage (Fedyuk & Meszmann, 2018; Perényi et al., 2012). Furthermore, wages at CEMs¹ can typically be lower than in other factories (Plank & Staritz, 2013). Additionally, in 2022, gross wages in the “Manufacture of computer, electronic, and optical products” (NACE 26) division amounted to HUF 537 112 on average, and net wages were HUF 357 179. The same year, gross wages in “Manufacture of electrical equipment” (NACE 27) were HUF 497 377 and net wages were HUF 330 756. However, it should be noted that these figures are distorted for two main reasons: First, they do not include the wages of agency workers – which are presumably lower – and wages of higher-paid workers tend to inflate the average, as reported and pointed out by Czirfusz (2022, pp. 34–35).

2.3.3. Occupational health and safety (OHS)

It is perhaps unsurprising to say that the majority of OHS problems stem from non-ergonomic working environments (Toldy, 2018a, 2018b). Workers frequently struggle with the long-standing, 12-hour shifts and disrupted sleep patterns due to the frequent alternation between multiple shifts. Fatigue, dizziness, high blood pressure, and other physical symptoms of stress are also common occurrences (Perényi et al., 2012).

Regarding accidents in NACE 26-27, more than half of them occur during production. In 2021, more than two-thirds of companies failed to comply with OHS requirements, including having issues with equipment, and problems with practices related to hazardous substances. Moreover, between 2008 and 2021, an average of 402-443 accidents per year occurred in NACE 26-27, respectively. Alarmingly, management often tries to blame accidents on worker negligence, as reported by Czirfusz (2022), based on data and information from the Ministry of Innovation and Technology and Department of Occupational Safety and Health.

¹ Contract Electronics Manufacturers

2.3.4. Representation of interests: Trade unions and works councils

Workers in Hungary are free to organize and engage in collective actions according to the Fundamental Law of Hungary (2011). Trade unions and work councils are the most common institutions for the representation of interests (Perényi et al., 2012). Temporary workers can join trade unions, but few of them do so, due to high turnover and language barriers (Czirfusz, 2022; Perényi et al., 2012). The attitude of companies towards trade unions varies greatly, but it tends to be hostile, especially among CEMs (Czirfusz, 2022; Plank & Staritz, 2013). On the other hand, the popularity of trade unions among workers has been damaged by their perceived association with state socialism (Perényi et al., 2012). Additionally, international financial institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) have also criticized trade unions for their strict working time regulations (Plank & Staritz, 2013).

Besides unions, works councils are mandatory for companies with over 50 workers, covering most of the Hungarian electronics industry (Perényi et al., 2012). These organizations are much more limited than trade unions, yet often workers don't know the difference between the two. Moreover, management frequently conveys the message to workers that works councils render trade unions redundant, thus reducing the need for them (Czirfusz, 2022). And the opinions of management and workers also differ regarding works councils, according to a study by Perényi and her colleagues (2012). Management prefers to see the works council as a forum for grievances and concerns, while employees believe that the real purpose of it is to disseminate information from management to employees (Perényi et al., 2012).

2.3.5. Foreign workers

A potential issue that foreign and other third-country workers may face in the Hungarian electronics industry is the restricted ability to freely switch workplaces, as they depend on the TWAs for their accommodation and resident permits, according to Czirfusz (2022). The latter which automatically terminated upon dismissal, which means they have to leave the host country within six days, potentially hindering their ability to find new employment and settle their residency affairs. This restriction is particularly a concern for non-European, third-country workers as, compared to Serbian and Ukrainian workers

who can stay in the country for 90 days at a time, or Ukrainians can apply for temporary protection status (Czirfusz, 2022).

Another characteristic of foreign workers is their remote location from their families as it contributes to their willingness to put in more overtime at work. This has led union organizers to express their concern that domestic workers' wages are under pressure from migrant workers. Followed by the resentment that foreigners get free accommodation, but locals don't get housing benefits (Czirfusz, 2022). However, the living conditions at workers' hostels may not always be ideal because these facilities only provide for a worker's most basic reproductive needs (Nagy, 2020).

2.3.6. Discrimination and violence

There persist a diverse range of workplace discrimination, violence, and conflict within the Hungarian electronics industry. Although the principle of equal treatment prohibits any form of discrimination between temporary and non-temporary workers, nearly 8% of workers have experienced some form of discrimination in the electronics industry (Czirfusz, 2022). To name a few, ethnic and nationality discrimination continuously was observed against Ukrainian workers compared to Hungarian workers. This manifests in unpaid overtime, shorter breaks, and even verbal abuse (Fedyuk & Meszmann, 2018). On the other hand, hostility and prejudice towards workers are made more difficult due to labor shortages (Czirfusz, 2022). When it comes to gender issues, the management typically fails to address the reported incidents such as sexual harassment, reducing the number of potentially reported cases and the sense of security for women workers (Czirfusz, 2022). Other reports by Perényi et al (2012) highlight harsh treatment by middle management. Strict discipline, prohibition of worker conversations, verbal abuse, inappropriate language, and threats of dismissal are all-too-common occurrences. In response, workers usually seek remedies through their line managers, while in some factories works councils facilitate communication between workers and management. Surprisingly, however, it is less common for workers to turn to trade unions for a solution (Perényi et al., 2012).

2.3.7. Gender issues

In addition to the harassment cases already mentioned, there are other systemic gender issues in the electronics industry. One significant concern is the pay and bonus systems, which disadvantage women, as they can lose out on substantial amounts of earnings due to the loss of bonuses stemming from caregiving responsibilities (Czirfusz, 2022). The uneven distribution of caregiving responsibilities between genders has profound implications for blue-collar women as it not only reduces their flexibility in working overtime or adapting to short-notice changes, but it doubles the burden on women, leading to a wide range of social and health problems (Criado-Perez, 2019; Fraser, 2016; Hochschild & Machung, 2012). Furthermore, migrant women, who are typically distant from their families, leave the responsibility for childcare to the family members left behind at home, typically to other women and grandparents (Kovály et al., 2017). Nevertheless, emotional labor may still fall on them due to the mental difficulties associated with maintaining family ties from a distance.

In summary, workers in the Hungarian electronics industry face many challenges regarding working conditions. Long and multi-shift work arrangements are coupled with living wages only achievable through extensive overtime and bonuses. Employers further complicate this with the time-banking system, and by providing short notice and irregular scheduling changes. Non-ergonomic working environments, high rates of accidents, and non-compliance with OHS regulations are also widespread occurrences. Furthermore, migrant and temporary workers are particularly vulnerable due to their reliance on TWAs. Additionally, migrant workers and women often face discrimination, and there is a prevailing hostility towards trade unions.

2.4. Adaptive strategies

2.4.1. Consent, coercion, and agency

Workers in a factory are subjected to various regulations, organizational techniques, self-disciplinary practices, and contractual obligations that reinforce the dominant work regimes (Foucault, 1995; Kuczi, 2011). However strong structural effects do not imply a complete lack of agency but merely describe the nature of the (social) space in which the

actors maneuver. To conceptualize this problem, it is useful to look at theories that attempt to synthesize agency and structure. Two concepts are invoked, one is Pierre Bourdieu's (1989, 2010) field theory, and the other is that of Michael Burawoy's² (1982) on coercion and consent manifesting themselves within factory environments. In the Bourdieusian (1989; 2010) theory of the social field, when actors enter specific fields – like the field of production – the logic and rules of the field weigh heavily on them and determine the room for maneuvering. Thus, individual and group strategies are also structural in origin, and action takes place in the social field in interaction with the institutions, networks, and actors within it. It is in this space that positions and dispositions, and power relations appear (Bourdieu, 1989; 2010). In this space, the workers utilize their different forms of capital (cultural, social, economic) in a Bourdieusian (1997) sense. For example, if workers' economic capital is relatively low, they are more likely to work overtime. During bargaining with supervisors, a lack of language skills or knowledge of local legal institutions, i.e. relatively low cultural capital, puts them at a disadvantage compared to the management. For migrant workers, social capital is of particular importance. Social capital serves as a valuable resource for workers, providing a broad spectrum of adaptive or exit strategies. It diminishes risks and the costs associated with adapting to a new environment through factors such as information sharing, mental and emotional support, decision-making advice, and finding accommodation, to name a few. If the workplace has an extended community, it can provide a sense of belonging, a form of safety net, and a familiar environment for people with similar habitus, in which workers can adapt more easily to hardships if needed (Bourdieu, 1997, 2002, 2009; Massey et al., 2012; Portes & Sensenbrenner, 2012; Sik, 2012).

As explained earlier, the history of modern capitalism is also the history of the coercion of labor (Kuczi, 2011). There is a reason why workers board the worker bus or get into their cars, and at the beginning of each shift, swipe their magnetic cards to spend the majority of their waking hours in a daily 12-hour routine across multiple shifts. To grasp this phenomenon, Michael Burawoy's (1982) ethnographic and sociological study titled *Manufacturing Consent* explains that social control peaks in wage labor, and manifests itself in consensus and sometimes, albeit not explicitly, latent conflicts. Using Burawoy's (1982) analogy of participation and subjection to industrial working conditions, we can

² Burawoy's work was influenced by Pierre Bourdieu, therefore it is easier to fit his theory with the theory of the social field.

imagine this as a “game” in which workers participate. In this system of relations, operators participate and compete, sometimes consciously or unconsciously. Burawoy (1982) describes this “game” as a ritual, a work environment embedded in a broader social context that helps endure coercion and obscures the burden of workplace power, and control. The most important takeaway is that their participation in wage labor implies consent to the rules, and the rules of the game are shaped by the interests of management and capitalist groups rather than by a democratic manner. Just as actors' room for maneuvering is set by the given social field.

Furthermore, most might think that interactions among workers could potentially enhance solidarity and improve working conditions. However, Burawoy (1982) draws our attention to the fact that since conflicts arising from work are mediated through an ideological terrain, and the work culture and hierarchical relationships of a particular factory, the conflict between workers and management can easily transform into competition among workers themselves: "*The translation of hierarchical domination into lateral antagonisms is, in fact, a common phenomenon throughout industry*" (Burawoy, 1982, p. 62), quoting Burawoy, who then references another study: "[...] *work pressure in general is negatively correlated to social supportive behavior. [...] Cohesive behavior is generally untenable under high-pressure conditions because the reward structure imposed by management directs employees to work as fast as they can individually.*" (Klein, 1971, p. 100, as cited in Burawoy, 1982, p. 62)

In summary, when workers enter the field of production, they are subjected to a complex set of regulations, internalized control mechanisms, hierarchical structures, and the logic of that given field in general, shaping their actions and the room for maneuvering. Bourdieu's field theory and Burawoy's concepts of coercion and consent shed light on the interplay between structural constraints and individual actions.

2.4.2. The typology of adaptive strategies

Adaptive strategies can vary based on countless factors. Comprehensively presenting the wide range of adaptive strategies of workers is, to say the least, beyond the scope of this paper. Instead, let's review some typical adaptive strategies that are observable when social actors perceive and leverage their agency, beyond simply resigning to the status quo.

Workers employ a diverse range of adaptive strategies to cope with deteriorating working conditions, which can be broadly categorized into three primary groups. The first category includes *individual adaptive strategies* such as resignation to working conditions and the development of various mental coping mechanisms. It also involves intensive labor, and, in some cases, individual negotiations with supervisors and superiors, as discussed by Burawoy (1982). And if all fails, changing the workplace is also an option for most of the workers.

The second category involves *interpersonal adaptive strategies*, such as competition, rivalry, passing the time together, or other particularities between several workers (Burawoy, 1982). Interpersonal adaptive strategies can also take a less passive form such as sabotaging each other. This can result from various reasons, including a lack of individual sympathy, different workloads, status inconsistencies, task-related problems, communication problems, and other wide-ranging sources of frustration (Black et al., 2019).

Finally, the third category comprises *collective strategies*. When it comes to changing precarious and flexible working conditions, trade unions typically come to mind. However, from the late 20th century, industrial unionism gradually lost strength and popularity (Crouch, 2017; Visser, 2012). Collective strategies also include strikes and other industrial actions, the practice and success of which depend greatly on the institutional background and wider social support (Dixon et al., 2004; Vesper & König, 2022). Moreover, there is a long history of demonstrations or even riots related to industrial working conditions. An example is the 2012 Foxconn workers' revolt (Chan et al., 2020) and a notable wave of protests in Hungary related to excessive overtime in 2018 (Gagyí & Gerőcs, 2019). Additionally, collective strategies include tactics such as work slowdown when workers intentionally slow down production or produce faulty products. The advantage of these strategies is that not all workers need to participate, as the interconnected nature of production compels other workers to slow down as well. Finally, an extreme strategy carried out by Foxconn workers involved threatening mass suicides and jumping from the factory roof if management did not negotiate with them about working conditions (Chan et al., 2020).

In summary, three main types of adaptive strategies can be drawn, individual, interpersonal, and collective. Each category represents a degree of solidarity, organized efforts, and formality in a passive or proactive sense.

2.4.3. Other factors influencing adaptive strategies of workers

Specific factors can assist in understanding the adaptive strategies of workers with diverse backgrounds and life situations. One of them is the form of employment that most directly impacts the lives of workers. It is more than a simple legal category. It is a social phenomenon with historical contexts. Temporary agency work, as one of the most flexible forms of employment, has important social implications, and it can be normalized as a standard practice among employers (Koene et al., 2004; Meszmann, 2018). Temporary agency work went through several iterations in Hungary (Kártyás, 2012). However, employment contract, whether open-ended, fixed-term, or through temporary agencies, greatly impacts social mobility, workplace relations, and individual perspectives (Meszmann, 2016, 2018). Going further, household characteristics and decisions greatly impact workers' strategies. Particularly among migrant workers where migration decisions reflect household adaptation to unevenly distributed economic opportunities and workplace dynamics (de Haas, 2011; Massey, 1990, 1999; Wallace, 2002). Finally, the 2022 invasion of Ukraine has triggered a significant wave of (forced) migration and opened up new social dynamics shaped by displacement, trauma, and the need for stability (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2023). Those migrants who did not pass through the country potentially found employment opportunities in Hungary (Előd, 2022).

3. Context: An overview of the electronics sector

This section delves into the electronics industry in Hungary, analyzing its sectoral employment statistics, including the role of temporary work agencies (TWAs), the regulatory framework, and the presence of foreign workers in the sector. This sectoral overview aims to provide additional insights besides the literature review and contextualize the analysis.

3.1. Employment and temporary work agencies in the Hungarian electronics sector

Hungarian electronics factories are important employers, usually employing between 600-4000 workers per plant (Czirfusz, 2022, p. 9). According to data from the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (2024) the Hungarian electronics industry directly employed 147 900 workers in 2022, fluctuating but growing from 2008. Within this workforce, 84 500 were engaged in the "Manufacture of computer, electronic, and optical products" (NACE 26) division, while 63 400 workers were employed in the "Manufacture of electrical equipment" (NACE 27) division.

According to data provided by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology (Gedei, 2022), a total of 33 362³ workers were employed by TWAs in the Hungarian electronics sector in 2021, making a significant increase from the previous years. In these divisions, 83% were employed with indefinite-term and 17% with fixed-term employment contracts.

It can be said that TWAs are a rapidly growing form of employment in Hungary. According to the Ministry of Innovation and Technology (Gedei, 2021, 2022), the number of individuals under contract with TWAs across all sectors has increased significantly. In 2005, the total number was 76 184, but by 2021, it had risen to 217 672, representing a 185.6% increase over the period and a 73.7% increase compared to 2020. In 2021, TWAs made contractual agreements with a total of 7 764 employers of which 394 employers belonged to the electronics sector. Furthermore, the demographic and employment data indicate that TWAs typically employ workers of active-working age, with low levels of education, mostly for unskilled and mechanical industrial tasks (Gedei, 2021; 2022).

In 2021, the NACE 26 division had one of the highest net revenue of HUF 47.05 billion⁴ among all divisions of the national economy. The growth was significant compared to the 2020 figure of HUF 17.46 billion. The same data in NACE 27 was HUF 27.73 billion in 2021, compared to HUF 6.13 billion in 2020, as reported by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology (Gedei, 2021; 2022).

In summary, the electronics industry in Hungary has seen fluctuations in employment rates but has grown following the global economic crisis. TWAs are becoming popular in

³ NACE 26: 23 382 and NACE 27: 9 980

⁴ " Coming close to the HUF 53.68 billion of "Vehicle manufacturing" division.

manufacturing and are a rapidly growing labor market service, representing a concerning shift toward flexible employment practices.

3.2. Regulatory framework of foreign workers

The regulatory landscape governing foreign workers in Hungary has undergone significant changes in recent years, causing difficulties for even the most experienced experts. The introduction of Government Decree 445/2013 (XI.28.) in 2017 was a turning point, simplifying the employment of citizens from specific third countries. This resulted in more Serbian and Ukrainian workers in the Hungarian labor market. Subsequent amendments including Government Decree 226/2022 (VI.28.), implemented in July 2022, exempt citizens from fifteen specified third countries from labor market examinations. However, only qualified TWAs are authorized to bring workers from the selected countries. Looking ahead, the 2023 XC. Law, effective in 2024, represents the Hungarian government's ongoing efforts to further regulate migration. It imposes restrictions on residency permits, titles of residency, and employment permits among others, particularly impacting labor migrants. The permits issued are valid for two years, extendable once, and reapplications are possible after three years. It's worth noting that changes in the workplace require a permit extension, which can be challenging for both workers and employers. Furthermore, family members cannot accompany workers, and if the worker's employment is terminated, they must leave within six days.

Overall, these changes reflect the Hungarian government's approach to managing foreign workers, to supplying cheap labor for industries, while inexplicitly addressing controversies regarding migration discourses.

3.3. Migrant labor dynamics in Hungary

One of the most comprehensive data regarding migrant labor in Hungarian manufacturing is provided by the annual reports issued by the Ministry of Economic Development (2023) and Ministry of Innovation and Technology (2022). Based on reports by these ministries, in 2022, a total of 32 660 work permits were issued in Hungary, excluding Ukrainian and Serbian citizens, 90% of which were issued to individuals from non-European countries (60% increase from the Philippines), representing a 33% increase

from the previous year. By the end of 2022, the total number of valid work permits was 51 328, representing a 67% increase compared to the previous year. As of the end of 2022, the number of valid permits issued to Ukrainian and Serbian nationals totaled in 60 443. Moreover, in 2022, employers reported 14 691 third-country workers from non-EU countries. The most workers were from the Philippines, with 3 981, followed by Romania with 1 858. The highest number of work permits issued in 2022 were for workers from Vietnam with 3 587, followed by India with 3 521, and South Korea with 2 455. Filipino citizens were issued 409 work permits, placing them in the 8th position based on their citizenship. Filipino citizens represented a total of 3 327 valid permits at the end of 2022. The “Labor Market Service” category dominated the issued permits, consisting of 55.5% for Serbian and Ukrainian workers. Moreover, 21.8% of third-country workers were also categorized under the same division highlighting a trend of temporary employment. Additionally, 10.7% of third-country workers were in the manufacturing, including the electronics sector. (Ministry of Innovation and Technology, 2022; Ministry of Economic Development, 2023).

Finally, in 2022, 93.6% of the work permits of citizens coming from Ukraine and Serbia were obtained for jobs not requiring specialized skills, compared to 46.8% for third-country workers (Ministry of Innovation and Technology, 2022; Ministry of Economic Development, 2023).

In summary, there is a rising trend of migrant labor in Hungarian manufacturing, particularly from non-European countries, with the majority of permits issued for low-skill and labor-intensive jobs. The increasing number of foreign workers employed through TWAs raises concerns about job security and bogus employment.

4. Research Questions

With the help of qualitative interviews and complementary field research methods, this paper seeks to answer the following research questions: 1) What are the general working conditions within the selected electronics industry plant? How do the flexibilization and precarization of work manifest within the factory? 2) Furthermore, what adaptive strategies do workers employ in response to flexibilization and precarization of work?

It is hypothesized that this study will reveal industry-specific working conditions that are consistent with the literature findings. Additionally, adaptive strategies will reflect individual-level actions and the acceptance of labor issues. With little or almost non-existent collective strategies.

5. Methodology

This thesis utilizes empirical data generated through a collaborative monitoring project involving the Periféria Policy and Research Center⁵ and Electronics Watch⁶. Using a method called *worker-driven monitoring*, to monitor working conditions, workplace abuses, and the general situation of workers in the Hungarian electronics industry while collecting evidence of potential problems, and then proposing possible solutions. The approach combines academic rigor with fieldwork, legal inquiries, social audits, and investigative journalism, with researchers working independently from the industries they monitor to protect workers' rights (Electronics Watch, 2020a, p. 5). This monitoring process has generated empirical data, suitable for academic repurposing. With the explicit and written consent of Periféria Policy and Research Center about data usage and the endorsement of both organizations, the empirical data generated during the first fieldwork are analyzed in this paper and is a noteworthy contribution to this thesis.

This thesis as a case study aims to uncover the working conditions in the selected electronics industry plant and explore the adaptive strategies workers employ in response. Given the complexity of these social processes, qualitative methodologies are employed to provide nuanced insights into workers' experiences.

The primary empirical material for this thesis is derived from field studies conducted between September 2022 and May 2023 at an electronics manufacturing factory in Hungary. Data collection primarily employed qualitative methods: ten semi-structured interviews were conducted with individual workers, and occasionally in small focus groups comprising two to four people. In addition to interviews, two unstructured

⁵ A Budapest-based independent think tank. The organization is committed to fostering connections between academic institutions, policymakers, market players, and the wider public. Employing advanced academic expertise and methodologies, they analyze market dynamics and their policy implications, particularly in areas such as housing, labor, and capital investments.

⁶ An international and independent not-for-profit organization that aims to help public buyers to protect and promote the rights and working conditions of workers in global electronics supply chains.

informal (group) discussions (with Filipino groups) were also utilized. Overall, nineteen workers participated in the qualitative study. Additionally, the research was supplemented by a review of work-related documentation provided by the participants.

Considering the demographic composition of the interviewees: Out of nineteen, thirteen are male and six are female. Their ages range from 18 to 50, with the majority falling between 20-40 years old. Regarding nationality, eleven interviewees are from Ukraine, seven are from the Philippines, one is from Hungary, and one person is from Romania. Three interviewees hold dual Ukrainian-Hungarian citizenship, and one holds Romanian-Hungarian citizenship. The tenure of the interviewees ranges from one to fourteen months, with an average of four months, indicating relatively high turnover rates. One Hungarian and two Ukrainian interviewees are directly employed by the company, while the rest are employed by four different temporary work agencies, mostly by TWA2, followed by TWA1. Concerning positions, the majority of them work as operators in various departments within the factory, and one is a production administrator.

In all cases, the interviews took place in person at the workers' accommodation, which allowed an insight into their living conditions, which is an important aspect concerning migrant workers. However, there were interviews (two) that had to be conducted in groups in a relatively short manner (15-30 minutes) while waiting for the workers' bus together. All other interviews took approximately 80 minutes on average, ranging from 45 minutes to 3 hours. Audio recording was made for almost all interviews, exceptions were made at the request of four interviewees. But they agreed to take notes. In addition to the formal interviews, in four cases 20-30-minute-long unstructured follow-up discussions were conducted with the interviewees by telephone calls. The interviews were conducted in Hungarian, Ukrainian, and English. For Ukrainian interviews, either a bilingual worker or an external interpreter assisted. In this thesis, the highlighted quotes were translated into English.

The questionnaires and interview guides used during the fieldwork were developed in consultation with partner organizations, following the guidelines of the Electronics Watch Code (2020b). Deviations from the interview guide were allowed during interviews and focus group discussions if they served to explore work-related issues or contribute to the success of monitoring activities. The questionnaires conducted during the field study were self-completed by thirty-six workers at the factory site, worker hostels, and worker bus

stops. The main function of it was to get an overall picture of working conditions and collect contacts for the later stages of the study. Unfortunately, the answers to the questionnaires were not included in this paper, but they served as a tool for developing the interview guide, validating the interviews, and collecting contacts for interviews.

The research involved two sampling methods regarding the interviews. Firstly, *convenience sampling*, a type of non-probability sampling method was used (Babbie, 2008, pp. 205–206), to reach the factory workers. Aimed to find locations where the largest number of workers were easily approached, as field experience suggested that workers were generally unwilling to participate in the research, especially local and higher-ranking employees. After the initial sampling, interviewed workers were asked to provide additional contacts, using another non-probability sampling technique called *snowball sampling*. This method is suitable for sampling hard-to-reach groups such as industrial and/or migrant workers (Babbie, 2008, pp. 206–207), who are often tired from excessive overtime and demanding industrial work and therefore difficult to interview. The methodology and sampling used in this study are relatively similar⁷ to the approach taken by Zsófia Perényi and her colleagues (2012) during a comparable action-oriented field study in the electronics industry in 2011-12. The exception is that in this part of the monitoring process to prevent the management from putting pressure on the workers during the research and to ensure the safety of the participants, the management and higher-ranking employees were not involved in the data collection.

Similarly, to Zsófia Perényi and her colleagues (2012), this study also ran into the challenge of collecting enough interviews per company. As in the mentioned research, entering the factory area was not an option, places had to be found where workers were directly reachable. These locations include the factory parking lot, the factory gate, nearby public places, bus stops, and workers' hostels. Due to low participation, it was decided with the partner organization to offer a grocery store voucher as an incentive for participation. This decision was made after long ethical consideration, after discovering that participants were hesitant to dedicate their limited free time, typically spent on reproductive work, to the monitoring activity. Additionally, despite the best efforts, it was

⁷ To avoid any misunderstanding: this research was not designed on the mentioned study. However, the challenges encountered with hard-to-reach participants and during fieldwork are very similar.

unable to include a sufficient number of local and core workers in the sample, resulting in an over-representation of migrant and temporary workers.

To analyze semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions⁸, and unstructured group discussions, thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) proved to be the more flexible and adequate approach, as it enables the analysis of different types of empirical data obtained during the field research. In addition to this, the content analysis of the work-related documents, and the analysis of sector-specific statistical data was used to get a more comprehensive picture.

The interviewee's name, the factory, and the temporary work agencies were anonymized, and detailed demographic information is also limited in this study to ensure the participant's safety.

6. Findings

6.1. Working conditions

6.1.1. Organization of work

The factory is an Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) employing between 1000 and 1200 workers. Concerning the employment status, apart from the core workers, four temporary work agencies (TWAs) employ workers for the factory, referred to anonymously as TWA1-4. TWAs employ some local workers, but most of the local workers are in core employment status. Most core workers are in managerial, supervisory, administrative, IT, engineering, or other senior positions. In contrast to Ukrainian and Filipino workers who account for more than half of the workforce and are typically employed by TWAs, in manual jobs. Core workers have open-ended contracts, Filipino workers have 1-year fixed-term contracts, and Ukrainian workers have 1-2 year fixed-term contracts of 40 hours per week.

There are three shifts in the factory, with night shifts introduced from August to October 2022, gradually across the factory. The night shift is reportedly run by separate teams,

⁸ In focus groups, participants interact within a group setting, potentially influencing each other's responses. When analyzing these groups, it's crucial to consider the dynamics, including consensus or dissent among participants. However, in this thesis, less emphasis was placed on the group dynamics within focus groups to facilitate addressing the main research questions. Priority was given to mutually reinforced information during the analysis process.

independent of the two day shifts. Ukrainian and local workers work night shifts, while Filipinos did not during the research.

There are two breaks (10 and 20 minutes) during the 8-hour shifts, and two additional 10-minute breaks if they work 12 hours. Breaks are too short to take care of tasks such as getting coffee, having a cigarette, and eating meals, according to the interviewees. This is due to the factory layout and slow turnstile gates. Failure to comply with the break time is penalized by the factory.

Shift managers manage the attendance list, but some workers claim that certified absences are regularly recorded as unjustified. Workers can take leave according to the law, but they have to keep 5-7 days for the end of the year. On average, two days off per month are allowed by management and usually, two weeks' notice is required. Workers are dismissed for three unexcused absences. Sick leave has to be certified, and the TWA's coordinator has to approve the request first. The production administrator, Zsófia is critical of the workers' sick leave, saying that most of them lie and take sick leave out of laziness. Therefore, "notorious cases" are sanctioned. Additionally, according to the production administrator, there was a problem with the time management system for several months resulting in incorrect recordkeeping.

Working hours are generally defined as 8-hour shifts, with 4 additional hours and Saturdays as overtime. Workers say that they are only required to work overtime a maximum of three times a month. The allocation of overtime is decided by the shift supervisor, specific to the department. Normally two Saturdays per month are compulsory as overtime, but it varies by department. In critical production departments, overtime cannot be declined. Overall, there is a contradiction in the workers' claims about overtime. They stress that it is possible to say "no" but it is not recommended, *"not worth the risk"* as told by Serhiy.

6.1.2. Seasonality of production

The level of overtime also depends on the cyclical or acute production demand, due to the delayed arrival of parts and the nature of public buyer purchases, as stated by a production administrator. Production demand is particularly high at the end of the year and quarterly closings. Workers worked overtime on three Saturdays in September. In

November, they signed a consent agreement for up to 400 hours of overtime. December is the most demanding period in which the *"minimum is 48 hours ... often there are more than 60 hours"* per week for workers, reports Zsófia, production administrator.

In addition to the compulsory overtime, often one worker is expected to do the work for two or three, which Andriy admits can only be sustainable for a day or two for a given worker. According to Kinga, there is a lot of “chaos” and “rushing around” during a peak production period, and workers rotated between different workstations.

"It's chaos inside [the factory]. Nobody knows what's going on [...] It would be so nice if it was more orderly [...] We're also running out of people. But they're also getting sick now. People are quitting more and more often. People are completely tired by the end of the year; everyone's overworked. It's chaos at work too. Disorganization has a big effect on people." – Kinga

The rotation of workers between work stages can be traced back to the drop-out rate of workers, the fact that they are subject to unpredictability, and mental and physical stress due to the high workload. Many fall ill from exhaustion, and many quit because they cannot or will not tolerate the pressure. And there is also a high probability of leaves (including sick leave) being denied by management.

In addition, workers also raised the issue of problematic overtime notice. In “good cases”, workers are given at least a day's notice, but interviewees said that it is too common to be noticed on the same day of overtime, resulting in problems with transportation and personal life issues.

In contrast to peak production periods, in downtimes, workers are sent on leave, typically at the expense of their days off. Interviewees resent this, as they think that they should be able to schedule their days off as they wish, they *"cannot help it if there is not enough work,"* said Serhiy.

6.1.3. Wages and compensation

Base salaries were between HUF 317-380 000 during the research, according to the contracts of interviewees. This is the basis on which wage supplements like bonuses and cafeterias are built. There have been two basic wage increases for operators and above since July 2022 due to inflation. Interviewees almost unanimously agree that basic wages

are not enough to live on. Only workers from the Philippines claimed that it was adequate for them, but added that just because they were single, the wages were much more "challenging" for those with families.

After the three-month probationary period, employees receive a bonus of between HUF 60-150 000. However, it turns out that, unlike workers from the Philippines, many Ukrainian workers do not receive this particular bonus, and the amounts vary.

There is no trace of a time-banking system. The interviewees stressed the importance of overtime, which is paid monthly, as it can significantly increase the wage. Saturdays represent 100%. Any additional 4 hours represents 50% wage supplement. According to the interviewees, several factors contributed to their willingness to work overtime. Foremost among these is the high cost of living. This is followed by the importance of family remittances, in the case of migrant workers. Workers also reported losing their entire monthly attendance bonus if they go on sick leave, in addition to too many written or verbal warnings, and sometimes do not get paid for overtime at the end of the month.

On top of this, workers are being urged by management and the TWAs not to talk to each other about their wages. According to the production administrator, the reason for this is because of the different bonuses, wage supplements, and hours worked. It only fuels wage tensions.

Apart from the probationary bonus, there is only an attendance bonus, which is 10% by the beginning of 2023. Workers don't feel informed about the bonus system and do not understand it. Workers believe that a more proportionate system is needed so that people do not lose their entire monthly bonus just because they are off sick, even if they have worked overtime for the whole month.

6.1.4. Occupational health and safety (OHS)

All employees receive OHS and fire safety training and fill out tests upon hiring and annually. There are also periodic customer audits where the correct use of protective clothing is checked, among others.

In case of accidents, there are first aid trained workers on every shift, but there is no doctor permanently on the shop floor, which was criticized by the interviewees. So, in case of accidents an ambulance is typically called. Regarding workplace accidents, the

company usually deflects them to the workers, and even interviewees emphasized the workers' responsibility.

Minor workplace injuries such as cuts and bruises on the hands were reported. Some employees also complained of heart problems and high blood pressure due to long hours standing and lack of fresh air. However, no direct exposure to toxic substances was reported by the interviewees.

6.1.5. Discrimination and violence

Concerning discrimination and violence, two main types of issues emerged from the interviews. One is related to the supervisors and the other to ethnic conflicts. In periods of peak production, supervisors can be harsh, causing mental and physical stress to workers. One line manager shouted at Tetiana, making her cry in front of the whole department. Workers were also threatened with dismissal or transfer if they didn't comply with demands. Managers also have been known to favor certain workers, with one manager telling a worker that he would make his job harder if he got to work with him.

About ethnic discrimination, management does not tolerate such behavior, at least openly. Additionally, according to the Ukrainian interviewee's perception, the management is generally less tolerant towards Ukrainian workers. But when it comes to concrete cases, interviewees tend to emphasize individual lack of sympathy, and interpersonal conflicts rather than ethnic conflicts. However, according to the production administrator, there are such conflicts, because: *"Ukrainians are by nature more temperamental and sensitive ... the Hungarians were like, 'I'm not working with them', the Ukrainians were like, 'I'm not working with those', and then you looked at the line like this, it's split in two."* – Zsófia

6.1.6. Cases of employment termination and mass layoffs

A significant factor in job insecurity is the threat of dismissal. This is reflected in several forms in the given factory. One case is that interviewees say that if a worker takes too much sick leave (typically 1-2 weeks) due to illness, they can easily be dismissed. The dismissal due to too much sick leave, according to the production administrator, came as a strategy from top management after it was suspected that workers were misusing it.

In addition to the occasional and methodical dismissals, during the field research, a mass layoff was witnessed that has not been seen in Hungary for many years. By December 2022 the factory started to employ Filipino workers, according to the interviewees. In January 2023, around 60-80 workers were working in the factory, and the interviewees estimated that there would be 150-300 more. Mykola claimed, based on rumors, that 40-60% of TWA workers were to be replaced at the beginning of the year. The new workers arrived after the peak production period and in parallel the factory started to dismiss some of the existing workers. Particularly Ukrainian and Hungarian workers employed through TWAs were reportedly the most effected. One of the most active agencies, TWA2, started hiring Filipino workers for the factory, and as a result, most of their workers were replaced. Later, TWA1 workers were also dismissed as the company also began to hire Filipino workers. In the interviewees' experience, management were dismissing around 10-15 workers a day, and several interviewees personally knew 10-20 workers who had been laid off. Workers were notified during, or after their shift to go to the TWA office to sign a mutual(!) agreement on contract termination, but several were informed by a Viber message: *"Hi, unfortunately [FACTORY] fired you. Come to the office tomorrow to sign the dismissal papers"*, as showed Mykola on his phone. The panic among Ukrainian workers ran like wildfire, and everyone feared he/she was next. Some of the interview contacts could not be reached during this period.

Temporary workers who were dismissed had to leave their accommodation within five days or the remaining days would be deducted from their salary, which was particularly difficult for Ukrainian workers with families fleeing the war.

TWA1 and TWA3 gave 15 working days compensation to workers, but TWA2 who brought the largest number of Filipino workers gave no compensation and the mutual agreement to terminate employment was highly unfair to the workers, which many signed only due to lack of information about the content, or because they were afraid of facing greater consequences if they did not comply.

6.1.7. Gender issues

The research did not focus directly and extensively on gender issues, but a few cases did emerge. For example, harassment is not tolerated by management. In addition, it has been confirmed that Filipino women are subjected to pregnancy tests before traveling. Going

forward, in two-earner households, parents often request separate shifts so that they can take turns looking after the children, but if both parents are working, the Ukrainian interviewees usually leave the children alone at the accommodation. Women with young children are not allowed to work night shifts either, but some mothers specifically requested to be transferred to night shifts so they can take care of their children during the day. Furthermore, pregnant women are not allowed to work overtime, and they cannot participate in production after a certain time. The production administrator noted, however, that more care should be taken when hiring pregnant women, as they cannot be counted on, nor can their partner.

6.1.8. The experiences specific to foreign workers

From a demographic perspective, the average age of Ukrainian workers interviewed in the study is around 36 years, skewed towards 40 years, typically with families and children, almost equally divided between women and men. The Filipino workers, in contrast, were typically men in their 20s with no family.

In the context of the recruitment procedure of migrant workers, the interviewees gained access to the factory via their social network. However, the recruitment procedure is slightly different between Ukrainian and Filipino workers. After the logic tests, contracts were signed collectively for Ukrainian workers in a larger group on arrival and there was not enough time to read it thoroughly. Serhiy expressed that he was not interested in doing so, saying *"no one is used to studying them anyway"*. He doubted that any changes would be made, even if he raised concerns. The recruitment process for Filipino workers is made more complicated by the geographical distance and the involvement of two different TWAs. Experience in electronics and fluency in English were prerequisites for employment. As part of the recruitment process, workers had to take a logic test and interview with the Philippines-based TWA and pass a medical examination. If these were successful then there was a personal interview with the TWA partner in Hungary (TWA2 and TWA1) who then set about preparing the necessary documents, visa, and residence permit. None of the TWAs deducted any costs according to the interviewees, but the TWAs paid for the paperwork and the travel, including the flight. The contract of Filipino workers is for one year, but if they leave the job early or get fired, they have to pay back the subsidies mentioned above to the TWAs, proportionally for the remaining months.

Asked how much this forced them to stay, Andres said: *"Yes, we are kinda forced to stay for a year, but rather as part of the contract"*. However, the Filipino interviewees had not yet experienced such a case because they had only been in the country for a few months. Andres mentioned having savings to cover additional costs, but other Filipino workers had to borrow money from relatives until they received their first salary in Hungary.

On the issue of language barriers, migrant workers often provided with Ukrainian or English interpreters, who are also operators. Ukrainian workers use this assistance daily. The employment contract is available in Ukrainian-Hungarian and in English-Hungarian, as for most of the work-related documents provided by the TWAs. The payslip is only in Hungarian, but workers eventually learn to interpret it.

Ukrainian workers have problems going to the doctor and getting sick leave certificates because of the language barriers. They often depend on TWA staff members who will undertake to go and interpret in person or over the phone, but it depends on the person and their availability. However, TWA coordinators often deny sick leave and they won't translate for them. According to Yana, she couldn't take any sick leave in eight months, so she missed work only three times to avoid being fired. The workers also say they get so much overtime compared to the locals because, unlike Hungarian workers, they can't argue with the supervisors due to language differences.

The Ukrainian and Filipino interviewees often feel that they are assigned more demanding jobs. Highlighting the feeling they are foreign workers; they can't laze around because they can easily be sent away. Conversely, Ukrainian workers feel that they are disproportionately treated more harshly and hostile by management, while Filipinos reported kindness at work. Although Ukrainian and Filipino workers are not hostile to each other, they also tend to cluster in groups with their own during work, breaks, and bus waiting.

In the context of the Russo-Ukrainian war, several worker's hostels allowed relatives, especially the children, to join in the accommodation for free, but as time went on, they were gradually forbidden to do so. One interview, for example, was interrupted twice by Mykola's daughter, who had to ask her father to sign her into an online class at her school in Ukraine. But many people, with the outbreak of war and the arrival of family, preferred to move further west. And after a while, Ukrainian workers found themselves facing

increasing tensions and uncertainty. Andriy mentioned that: *"Ukrainians work a lot to come here and they wanted stability. They take on all the work, and in the end, they end up with their bonuses being deducted for all sorts of reasons."* According to Tetiana, many Ukrainians don't get their probationary bonus because the days they spend at the immigration office are recorded as uncertified absences by the line managers.

6.1.9. Living conditions

The accommodation is typically rented and provided by the TWAs to their temporary workers, free of charge, while core workers resent the foreign workers because they do not have housing support.

Since most interviews were conducted in workers' hostels, I was able to gain insight into the living conditions of the workers, in addition to the interviewees' accounts. Eszter, Gábor, Vasyl, and Serhiy lived in completely different types of accommodation than the rest of the interviewees. They were living in a high-capacity workers' hostel converted from an office building on the outskirts of the city, as several agencies and several employers rented rooms to their workers. The receptionist said it could accommodate more than 150 people. There are two to three beds per room, with a shared kitchen and bathroom on each floor, which is too under-equipped for the number of people living on the floor. Residents complained about cockroaches (which I also saw in the kitchen when I opened an oven). There was also extensive mold in the bathroom and the room of the interviewee. One toilet was unusable, the shower curtains also were covered in mold, and there was standing water in the bathroom, the walls looked thin and the vent running along the walls of the building was full of rubbish and accumulated dust. The windows of the building were covered in many places with reflective silver material, presumably to keep out sunlight and heat. Residents are not allowed to have guests at night, only during the day (The receptionist argued that the workers would otherwise be bringing in "prostitutes"). There are no community areas at the accommodation. Serhiy cited the occasional noise, drunken behavior, and occasional fights between the residents, which more than once ended with police intervention. This was also backed up by the receptionist.

In contrast, the other interviewees were living in four separate, newly renovated private apartments, repurposed as workers hostels, rented by the TWAs. These were in much

better condition than the high-capacity hostel mentioned above and could accommodate 20-30 people, in two to three person rooms, with couples typically sharing a room. These buildings typically had a large, equipped kitchen and shared bathrooms. The residents were typically divided by nationality and origin. None of the interviewees was able to answer the question of how the agencies decide who gets what accommodation besides segregation by nationals. These private residential accommodations typically have a courtyard that can be used by residents for community events at weekends. But even in these hostels, residents are not allowed to receive guests, which makes life difficult for workers with families.

Ukrainian workers typically complained more about the accommodation, while Filipino workers seemed more grateful. One of the building maintainers said that Filipinos had asked for bicycles and a small plot of land in the communal yard where they could grow vegetables, which was provided. He also added that he personally prefers Filipino workers, *"better than the Ukrainians and Hungarians because at least they are grateful and clean every day"*.

Finally, workers face housing insecurity if they are dismissed or quit. They must leave the accommodation within days and pay a daily fee if they want to stay longer.

6.1.10. Temporary work agencies

As reports have shown, TWAs are present in all aspects of production and leisure. Just over half of the workers are employed by four TWAs and the majority of these are of Ukrainian origin as already mentioned. TWA workers have a high turnover rate. Not only is it easier to fire TWA workers, but according to the production administrator, they are more likely to quit if they have a problem. The policy for termination of the contract is two weeks for agency workers, but many do not work at this time. The factory does not typically respect this either. Ukrainian workers can stay in the country after being resigned or laid off and typically move on to Europe or another company locally, but Filipino workers lose their permits within six days if their employment is terminated. Many of them could not answer what happens when their one-year contracts expire, but Andres, for example, sees his job as a steppingstone to other European countries.

According to the production administrator, the TWAs stress to their workers that their primary employer is not the factory but themselves. The workers are in regular contact with the TWA mostly either via Viber or in person during office hours. The workers can contact their coordinators who typically speak several foreign languages.

Ukrainian workers think they are better off being employed through TWA rather than directly because they can take care of all the paperwork, banking, medical appointments, and even translation, not to mention free housing. So, they both benefit from and depend on these services. Meanwhile, the interviews also reveal a lack of trust on the part of the workers towards the TWAs, as they do not always trust that they will be paid properly by the company. Zsófia, a production administrator, said in the interviews that she had conducted a survey among TWA workers with the help of HR and found that *“they don't necessarily have a good relationship with the rental companies [TWAs]. They don't feel informed, they doubt that the amount they get is actually good, if they ask for help they feel shaken off.”* – Zsófia.

No direct wage differentials were identified between TWA and core workers. Interviewees were also divided on who gets paid more and who gets paid less. However, Zsófi said that as a core worker, the employment relationship is more stable, and it is easier to solve workplace problems with HR than with TWAs and stressed that temporary workers are easier to dismiss.

6.2. Adaptive strategies

During the interviews and field study, adaptive strategies for precarious working conditions were evident in both implicit and explicit forms despite not being part of the interview guides. Not only did workers share their thoughts on working conditions, but there is also a demand among the workers interviewed to improve their situation. Beyond the problems of base wages, most interviewees replied that they would be happy if management gave workers at least one day's notice before overtime. Followed by the bonus system being revised to be more transparent and fairer. Furthermore, the interviewed workers shared a desire for the management's attitude to be improved to reduce favoritism, and for the quality of accommodation to be improved.

In the following paragraphs, the adaptive strategies shared by workers are presented, broken down into types along individual, interpersonal, and collective categories.

6.2.1. Individual strategies

According to the findings individual problem-solving dominates in worker attitudes and practices. If there is a problem, workers either go to the line manager, to the shift manager, to HR, to administrators, or TWA coordinators, individually. If the workers cannot solve their problems with a particular supervisor, they typically go to the person above them in the chain of command. Workers usually go to their line or shift manager for operational issues, or to production administrators for administration and record-keeping. If they have problems with their supervisors, they go to the administrators or HR. TWA workers usually go to the TWA when they have problems, but they are don't know who to with problems of TWA.

Highlighting the most frequent individual strategies, perhaps the most common strategy for workers to supplement their low base salary is to work overtime. There are two main ways of doing this. The first is that the shift supervisor sets the overtime, and the worker simply goes to work. Accepting it passively, within the formal framework. A more active form of this is when the worker requests overtime:

" [...] there are people that really - I just look at it - are in for 5 days, 12 hours, and they come in on Saturday ... and I look at it like, I'm tired of seeing your time sheets. Good. And he can take it because he's from a manual job, so he came from construction and stuff, and he's used to working a lot." – Zsófia

As this quote points out, factors affecting overtime work include previous work experiences. Another factor is whether the worker's labor is needed at the time, which is a market factor. A third factor is the family status. Migrant workers tend to work overtime because of the need to support the family, to send money home for the family, and the distance from the family alone can be a motivating factor for working overtime. And finally, the perception of power relations and agency may push workers, especially migrant workers to say yes to overtime: *"I think part of that is because we're foreigners in this country. So we are under a specific contract from our agency. So we have to protect,*

we have to do whatever it takes to not mess up anything. Because if you did mess up, you're going to go back home." – Andres

In contrast to this, it also happens that workers get tired, are fed up with the workload, and then resist overtime: *"So, we've had people in the departments who have said, 'listen, I worked 12 hours all last week, I was in on Saturday, if you tell me to stay in, I'll kick you' ... So there are people who really say, 'listen, I don't want this overtime in the middle of my back'"* – Zsófia

Because of the low base wage, bonuses are an important factor in workers' earnings. Almost monthly, TWA or administrators are contacted individually by workers to correct perceived or real administrative errors regarding attendance, certified or un-certified leave, and any other factors that lead to the loss of bonuses. The willingness to take personal advocacy related to records is heavily affected by language differences. *"It's harder for Ukrainians to do anything here if you take it because without an interpreter you can't [do much]"*, Vasly said. So, the availability of interpreters and or the individual language skills of the worker affect the willingness and the outcome of individual strategies.

Leaves are an important part of workers' lives, especially if they fall ill. However, as has been reported, supervisors and TWAs are reluctant to let workers go on sick leave, especially during periods of peak production. This leads to workers going to work sick resulting in a passive adaptive strategy, giving in to coercion. However, factors such as the relationship with the TWA coordinators, and supervisors, and the degree of feeling sick also influence this. The war has led some Ukrainian workers to value their days off more, as some of their relatives have also moved to the country with them. Additionally, a related adaptive strategy is for workers to take sick leave (if they can) when they do not get regular leave. In such cases, there are two strategies for workers to avoid or minimize the financial loss: *"Either get a certificate of absence and then get the [attendance] bonus or get a sick leave paper and then get 70% of the daily salary but lose the bonus for the whole month"* – Zsófia.

Going forward with resignation, as an individual strategy, if workers are not happy with the factory for various reasons, such as low wages or overwork, as in the peak production periods, they will simply quit and leave. Since workers have individual contracts, they bargain individually with supervisors and TWA staff, and the mechanism of resignation

is considered as an individual act, nevertheless, the reasons and the context are structural. Local workers typically spend a couple of days before deciding to leave. Just like some Ukrainian workers, who just "look around" and move on. Workers typically go to other countries or try other factories in Hungary. Quitting is an individual or household decision, but it is also influenced by other factors beyond wages, by financial situation, and the extent of informal networks that an individual has. Other factors in the findings include seasonality of production, dependence on TWAs for work, residence permits or visas, and other labor market characteristics: *"Generally what I hear is that they won't leave because 'I have a job now, they won't hire me anywhere else by December'"* - Zsófia pointing out the seasonality of the resignations, that increases at the beginning of the year in her experience. Finally, resignation is also influenced by how workers perceive the general economic situation. Dániel says that *"at these prices, it would be difficult for me to change jobs"*, adding that in the past, changing jobs was quick and easy for him.

During the mass layoffs, workers have quit rather than be fired. So did Vasyl when he saw his colleagues and friends being laid off one after the other. Others of the Ukrainian workers resigned because the TWAs fired their partners, and instead ended up looking for a new job together.

Additionally, during the mass layoff, TWA2 did not give the workers any compensation upon dismissal, but Mykola learned from his co-workers that the TWA1 workers had been given it. Therefore, Mykola and Petoro, individually, were able to arrange at the TWA office to terminate their contract instead of signing a mutual agreement thus getting compensation.

6.2.2. Interpersonal strategies

An example of interpersonal strategies occurred when, during layoffs or peak production periods, workers advised each other that it might be better to look for another job: *"They say it's better to work at [Company]"* – Kinga

"Word gets around, they're already talking amongst themselves to look for another job because they're going to fire everyone who's Ukrainian by May." – Kateryna

Two further interpersonal strategies have emerged, one is that workers often try to get on good terms with their supervisors, which makes it easier for them to obtain occasionally

advantageous arrangements. Some workers find this difficult and find "suck-ups" "tiresome" and frustrating and see this behavior as favoritism.

Finally, another strategy found in workers sabotaging each other at work to put themselves in a relatively better position. An example of this was seen during the mass layoffs. According to Mykola, some workers would target each other's work areas and "*chop wood under each other*" so that management would have a better chance of issuing a warning to those workers, increasing the likelihood of dismissal.

6.2.3. Collective strategies

Concerning the more conventional form of representation of interest, in the factory no trade union or works council was found, the latter of which is mandatory. Serhiy does not see any sense in a works council because: "*For Ukrainian workers it is superfluous [...] because we don't know the language, people don't know the language anymore, even through an interpreter it's useless... it's like peas vomited on the wall.*" – Serhiy. Showing that the language barrier can be an important factor in organizing among Ukrainian workers and that the concept of collective advocacy is also distant. According to the production administrator, there had been an attempt to unionize the workers in one of the larger departments of the factory, but this initiative eventually died. There was no further information as to the exact context in which this happened and why it did not take place.

And the final finding on a collective strategy relates to the accommodation. In the high-capacity hostel presented, living conditions were drastically bad, therefore the residents had started to raise the issue within the factory. TWAs in response relocated the residents into private apartments, with better living conditions: "*New hostel is good, we can live in separate flats. Many people reached it together. It's a good thing.*" – Gábor

6.2.4. The role of coercion and power relations

Even if implied or directly presented in the previous parts of the findings, it is worthwhile to highlight the role of coercion and asymmetrical power relations regarding adaptive strategies. Namely, that the employees are afraid to stand up for themselves because they fear the wrath of their supervisors:

"If they bring up something, trying to stand up for their rights or explain the situation or something. They [the supervisors] immediately come up with the idea that it's a conflict and you should be fired because you creating a conflict. ... And they [the supervisors] always said that if you don't like something, you can go out the door." – Andriy and Kateryna

"They also dismissed people who dared to speak back or stand up for their rights" – Yana

For example, Andriy and Kateryna are afraid to turn off overtime because they fear "hellish working environments", others are afraid of being perceived as untrustworthy and becoming "snitches". This is amplified by the narrative of reciprocity that was repeatedly brought up by the production administrator and interviewees. That is, management is only fair to workers if the workers are fair to the factory.

7. Discussion and Conclusions

This study used qualitative interviews, field studies, and thematic analysis to explore trends in the flexibilization of work and precarious employment in a selected electronics manufacturing plant in Hungary. The aim is to understand flexible practices reflected in the working conditions and what adaptive strategies workers employ in response.

To answer the first part of the first research question about the general working conditions, it can be concluded that in the researched factory, temporary work agencies (TWAs) employ a significant portion of the labor force. More than half of the workforce mainly consists of Ukrainian and Filipino workers in addition to local workers. Temporary and foreign workers are typically employed in low-skilled positions with 1-2 year-long fixed-term contracts reflecting precarious employment practices. Employees involved in production work multiple shifts and long 8-12 hour working days, even on weekends. Workers complain that the breaks are too short for employees to replenish. Regular overtime is recommended in general, but during peak production periods is mandatory. Workers are incentivized to work overtime to earn bonuses and wage supplements for not having enough base wages to live on, especially if they have families. Management is strict about allocating regular and sick leaves in general, which if too much is accumulated the employee can easily be dismissed. Recordkeeping errors related to attendance seem to be more of a feature than an anomaly, due to its systematic and methodological

occurrence. And the worker's accommodation is only adequate for the basic reproduction of the labor power. The presence of foreign workers provides flexibility for employers. On the one hand, they are provided with free accommodation and a wide range of services but are associated with relatively high turnover rates. On the other hand, the language barriers, power imbalance within the employer-employee relationship, their dependency on the employers, and general vulnerability make foreign workers an optimal workforce, which is likely to provide a return on the resources invested in TWA services, from the perspective of the employer. Therefore, the findings present a pattern in working conditions that is prevalent in the Hungarian electronics industry (Perényi et al., 2012; Meszmann, 2016; Czirfusz, 2022), which is a co-production of the local policy environment and the global division of labor (Czirfusz et al., 2019; Gerócs & Pinkasz, 2019; Plank & Staritz, 2013).

To answer the second part of the first research question regarding flexibilization and precarization of work within the factory, it is important to understand the reasons why factories implement these practices in the first place. To answer this, let's revise the foundation for analysis and describe the wider structural conditions.

The researched factory does not exist in a vacuum, it is embedded in regional and global structures, embedded into the global division of labor (Gerócs & Pinkasz, 2019). Wages need to be aligned with regional or national wages. This is the price of proximity to European markets for multinational companies. In addition, companies must remain competitive, meet deadlines and production demand, and align strategies with the logic of the global supply chain, to accumulate capital for their investors (Plank & Staritz, 2013). These structural contexts drive the seasonality of production, the work organization practices including overtime practices and record keeping, workload, supervisory decisions and behaviors, low wages, and job insecurity concerning the form of employment, as reported in the findings. To put other words, when the management of the factory integrates the worker's labor and time into the production in a flexible manner including short overtime notice, mandatory overtime, or declining leaves, it can optimize production, reduce costs, and eventually improve profitability for the employer (Timár, 1988). From the perspective of workers, this results in a constant feeling of uncertainty concerning their work schedules, free time, wages, and employment status as it was found. However, workers still participate in these practices because of the low base wage and financial incentives such as bonuses, and the vulnerable position stemming from

temporary or migrant status. They are willing to tolerate the precariousness of their livelihoods and working conditions in less optimal economic conditions, combined with mechanisms of consensus and coercion on the factory floor (Burawoy, 1982).

Going further, to explain the extensive use of temporary employment and migrant labor – as another set of practices used by the industry – it's important to remember that the electronics supply chain is sensitive to global influences (Perényi et al., 2012), and for capitalist production to work effectively, it's crucial that its various components, including the workforce, can adapt to changes in production and market conditions. This leads to flexible working conditions allowing employers to use working time and labor power more efficiently, to reduce production costs, increase competitiveness, and accumulate capital as explained by Timár (1988). This is a product of industrial development in the latest stages of global capitalism (Harvey, 1989). In these already presented developments, the globalization and the flexibilization of production go hand in hand with the globalization and flexibilization of labor, increasing the levels of global labor migration (Harvey, 1989; Melegh, 2004). From the perspective of capital, by employing migrant workers, companies complement the particularities of the local labor markets, as migrant workers tend to be employed in sectors and positions that are less attractive to the local labor force (Massey, 1999; Piore, 1979). This explains why the interviewed workers, just as the migrant, and the temporary workers, in general (Gedei, 2021; 2022; Ministry of Innovation and Technology, 2022; Ministry of Economic Development, 2023), are typically employed in low-skilled, manual jobs. Furthermore, companies in the sector are tapping into existing practices when it comes to the workforce since the importation of labor has already established institutions and markets. In this way, migration processes induced by the importation of labor are produced and reproduced cumulatively (Massey, 1990; 1999). TWAs are integrated into this phenomenon since it is this labor market service that functions as a mediator between capitalist companies and the labor force. The rising number of temporary workers and their growing profits, especially in manufacturing (Gedei, 2021; 2022), highlight how flexible labor practices are becoming more common. This trend has worrying implications for the workers hired by these agencies, as shown by the findings.

Going forward with TWAs and migrant workers, an interesting labor market change also unfolded during the fieldwork, which could influence the situation of foreign workers in Hungary in the coming years, in my opinion. The perception and situation of Ukrainian

workers and their labor market situation in Hungary seem to have resulted in changing trends since the Russian-Ukrainian war, according to the findings. The turnover rate of Ukrainian workers was already high before the direct armed conflict, due to the extensive networks, and extensive experiences in migrating, but they were nevertheless available for the companies as a cheap labor force (Fedyuk & Kindler, 2016). Interviews suggest that it has become increasingly difficult for Ukrainian workers to fit into the flexible labor regime since the Russian-Ukrainian war, at least in this particular factory. The results implicate a conflict of interest between the need for stability among Ukrainian workers and the precarious employment found in the factory. This coupled with scarce accommodation, the high cost of living, and the double burden resulted from caregiving responsibilities and blue-collar work. Additionally, with the increased (forced) migration, Ukrainian workers become more mobile than before, as migrant networks increased with the increased levels of actors within it, potentially resulting in new job opportunities within it. This increased mobility, with a desire for stability, may have caused discontent among the Ukrainian workers, resulting in issues with their working and living conditions and wages, in my interpretation. This potentially made them a problematic group in the eyes of management, as they may be demanding better pay, taking more leaves, or leaving their jobs more frequently. This assumption is reinforced by the increasing intolerance and hostility from the management toward Ukrainian workers, and the motive of friendliness towards Filipino workers, as perceived by the interviewees. Concluding that, the layoffs described in the findings are, in my view, a response to the increased mobility and problems associated with Ukrainian workers, on the part of the factory management. Therefore, the factory is adapting to the changes by diversifying its labor force by importing Filipino workers. They are not the first to do so in Hungary, but they are clearly among the first. And in the TWAs' strategy, this process and their partnership with the Philippine-based TWAs can easily be called an "innovation", as they could offer an alternative to an acute problem, thus preserving their competitive position. This is also confirmed by media reports from TWA representatives explaining that it is more expensive and time-consuming to hire Filipino workers compared to other options, but at least companies can build a stable workforce around them (Németh, 2024). This is further backed up by the findings that Filipino interviewees are much more dependent on their employer due to the geographical distance, high recruitment cost, and resident permit. Point in the direction of more predictable workplace behavior and better fit with the labor needs in the Hungarian electronics sector.

Finally, the dismissal of TWA workers without warning, and the forced signing of the mutual agreement contract on the employment termination, point to the high level of job insecurity of TWA workers. It also shows strategic consideration on the part of the factory management to wait until the end of the peak production period before making the dismissals, so as not to undermine production and their own business.

Following with the second research question concerning the adaptive strategies employed by the workers in response to working conditions. Workers are not just passive victims of the structural effects of their employment. They also have a degree of relative agency and preferences. For example, according to the findings they want to be informed on time about overtime so that they can regain control over their free time. If they want to reform the bonus system, it's because they desire a more secure and predictable wage system. When they aim to change the attitude of management, it can be interpreted as a desire for more relaxed authority and a more humane working environment. The question is how this and similar demands meet the objective conditions already outlined.

Of the three groups of adaptive strategies to precarious and flexible working conditions, individual strategies emerged as the most utilized form of action in the findings. These are typically passive strategies such as working more overtime when the base wage is low or going to work when sick to avoid losing the bonus. When a problem arises, or workers are distrustful about pay and recordkeeping, they use a set of strategies that are mostly aligned with the grievance mechanisms already found in the workplace, using the channels provided by supervisors, the HR office, and TWA coordinators to individually address and improve their situations.

Among interpersonal strategies, Burawoy's (1982) and Klein's (1971) claim that strong hierarchical relationships and work pressure do not necessarily lead to social supportive behaviors but to competitive behaviors among employees, such as sabotaging co-workers or individual bargaining and relationship building with management, seems to be confirmed. If solidarity emerges, it is in the form of information exchange, on which workers can build individual or household strategies.

Finally, in the absence of trade unions and works councils, no other collective adaptive strategy was observed, except for the replacement of the bad workers' hostel. The absence of a compulsory works council also shows that if it were up to the management there would be no collective and institutionalized grievance mechanism in the factory.

Furthermore, the fragmentation of the workforce along nationalities, languages, and the four TWAs and core workers' employment status makes formal or informal collective advocacy difficult.

Upon examining adaptive strategies in relation to nationality, employment form, and contexts, it was found that individual strategies appear in all interviews, almost without exception, regardless of nationality or form of employment. Within that, overtime work is influenced by the workers' previous work experience, their family status, or migration status, and the need for labor power in specific periods. However, the resignations are related to Ukrainian workers only, and are contextually related to the peak production period and the mass layoff period. This is influenced by the extent of the worker's network, perceptions of the general economic situation, labor market characteristics, and dependence on TWAs or employers for residence permits. Interpersonal strategies, including the sabotage of colleagues and job offers within the network, are similarly linked to layoffs, and the peak production period, and were discussed by Ukrainian workers, most typically those who were directly or indirectly involved in the dismissals. The collective adaptive strategies emerged among Ukrainian workers who were accommodated in a high-capacity worker hostel after they realized the status of their accommodation relative to other hostels. In contrast, Filipino workers were found to have adopted a "wait-and-see" approach, since they have been in the country and have been working in the factory for a relatively short period of time. They are also more dependent on their employer for residence permits and, in a broader sense, still lack certain local and institutional knowledge in their new environment, which may temporarily reduce their room for maneuver.

Workers typically respond by adopting adaptive strategies at the individual level, exploiting channels already present in the workplace. These are the actions and mechanisms that workers find in the field by default when they enter it by contractual agreements and participate in production. They follow the logic of the given social field that functions in a way that reproduces and sustains itself (Bourdieu, 2010). The fact that there is no formal form of collective bargaining, neither a trade union nor a compulsory works council, reduces the room for maneuver of the actors, as the logic of production can be more strongly enforced. Well-established and widespread practices of individual bargaining erode potential group formation. This is further reduced, in my view, by the fact that workers are fragmented by nationality and employment form. Therefore, upon

entering the factory gates, workers participate in the “game”, which implies consent to the rules as established by Burawoy (1982). And if there is no formal or informal institution to set the rules other than the management, the strategies that workers can use in their interests are drastically reduced. And these institutions are historically in decline not only in the electronics sector but globally in general (Crouch, 2017; Visser, 2012).

The instruments of coercion at work that supervisors consciously or unconsciously use, such as the role of authority, hostility towards workers or a group of workers, favoritism, and denial of the worker's requests, all reinforce the rules found in the field of production. The relative agency of workers is further reduced by the fact that in the absence of collective strategies, individual bargaining and lobbying of the workers are more optimal for the employer, who can easily assert their interests. While financial struggle and incentives in the factory further support the consensus on working conditions.

Finally, in the case of migrant workers, migration discourses (Melegh, 2006) in which local decision-makers and local employees describe and see migrant workers, and in which the perception of migrants' relative agency decreases due to their foreignness, evoke a kind of distinction mechanism (Bourdieu, 1989). This not only means that the field of action is objectively diminished – although in some legal and institutional terms, it is objectively diminished for migrant workers –, but it also implies that the imagination of potential actions is diminished for migrant workers as they internalize migrant discourses. In these settings, global political-economic positions and structural power relations seep into the shop floor of the factory, and in the relations of workers and management, reproducing existing social structures.

Based on the findings of the fieldwork conducted on working conditions in the Hungarian electronics industry, it can be concluded that the factory under study exhibits similar working conditions and practices of flexibilization and precarious employment as other factories in the industry. This is done to remain competitive and profitable. To achieve this, the factory uses strategies such as adapting production components to market processes with regulation of working time and leaves, organizing work within the factory to ensure control and seamless production, and employing migrant and temporary workers as a cheap and precarious labor force. In response, workers tend to adopt mainly individual adaptive strategies, utilizing existing channels in the workplace. Global social

structures are reproduced in the relations between workers and employers in the factory by coercion, consensus, and various distinction mechanisms.

The study has relevance as it produced up-to-date findings related to Ukrainian workers in Hungary and described labor market changes relating to the arrival of third-country nationals and its impact on existing workers. Furthermore, the study was able to demonstrate the implication of temporary employment on working conditions. Each of these three topics deserves further in-depth research.

Finally, the study has some limitations that need to be considered. Firstly, as it is based on qualitative methods, the results cannot be generalized. Additionally, the study only touched upon the topic of adaptive strategies as the empirical findings related to it were discovered incidentally during the monitoring of working conditions. Therefore, to gain a better understanding of the adaptive strategies of workers in manufacturing, further targeted and systematic research is needed.

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9. Appendices

9.1. Interview guide

Please introduce yourself /tell us about yourself.

How old are you? / Where are you from?

Please tell us about your experiences at [COMPANY].

What do you like and dislike about your job? /How long have you been working at [COMPANY]? /Are you a direct employee or employed through a TWA? /How long is/was the contract for? / (Why did you leave/dismissed?)

Please describe how you found your current job. Tell us about the recruitment process.

Tell us about the department you work in at the [COMPANY]. (Specify relevant departments within [COMPANY])

Please tell us about your work schedule.

On average, how many overtime hours do you work per week? / How are the breaks organized in your workplace? / Is overtime mandatory in your current position? / We heard that it's mandatory to work 1-2 Saturdays per month. Is that true, and what determines which Saturdays? /Tell us about overtime. Any arise from late notices? /Is the amount of overtime the same for pregnant or single-parent employees?

How do you feel about your salary?

Can you make a living from the basic salary without overtime? /Please tell us about the bonus system and salary supplements

What is [COMPANY] 's position if someone is absent from work for some reason?

Has anyone been dismissed for taking too much sick leave? / We heard that workers lose attendance bonuses if they take too much sick leave. / What motivates workers to come to work even when sick?

What are your experiences with your supervisors?

Who do you turn to if you feel that something is unfair? / Have you or any of your colleagues ever been threatened with dismissal? / How common is it for supervisors to shout at people? / Are there famously bad supervisors?

Have you had a colleague whose employment was terminated improperly?

What happened? / Have you been threatened with dismissal?

Please tell us about how safety-related issues are handled at your workplace.

Do you work with hazardous substances? / How does the [COMPANY] communicate about these substances? / Did you have health training before starting work? / What health services does the [Company] provide? / Is there a doctor or nurse on-site in the [COMPANY]? / How easy is it to reach them? / Have you or someone you work with been involved in an accident at work? Please share your experience. / What are the consequences of accidents at work? / How does your workplace handle accidents? / In case of injury, who can you turn to? / Who approves sick leave? / Do employees supporting health care receive compensation? / How do the [COMPANY] ensure that the machines do not cause injuries? Is there regular maintenance? / Is there fire- or other emergency drills in the [COMPANY]? / Are informative OHS materials available throughout the factory? (Pictures, texts, pictograms etc.)

How easy is it to obtain information about salary slips and other administrative processes, procedures, etc., in the [COMPANY]?

Is the salary slip accessible? / Are these documents also available in multiple languages?

What do you think are there any differences between core workers and temporary agency workers?

Do you think workers employed through TWAs are in a more disadvantageous position than those working directly for the [COMPANY]? / In your opinion, what could be the advantages and disadvantages of being directly employed in [COMPANY]? / Are foreign workers also subject to the same schedules, overtime, etc.?

Have you experienced any form of discrimination? / Have you or your coworkers experienced any form of discrimination based on gender, ethnic background, or sexual orientation in the electronics industry? (Ask this question more specifically, along the lines of concrete examples)

(If living in workers accommodation) How do you find the living conditions in the worker accommodation? (General satisfaction)

How did you arrange your housing? How did you get your current housing opportunity? / How many people live in one room?

If you could change one or two things about your current workplace in the [COMPANY], what would they be?

How easily could you change your workplace? (If not, why?)

Have there been any initiatives to organize a local trade union?

Is there a works council in the factory?

Is there anything we haven't discussed that could be important?

Do you have a friend or colleague in the [COMPANY], with whom we could conduct a similar interview?

Can we take photos of the contract, salary slip, confidentiality agreement, or other work-related documents? (Optional: heavily depends on context, trust, situations etc.)